

The Vulvovaginal Symptom Questionnaire The following questions were developed to assess skin symptoms of women. The skin surrounding the vagina is called the vulva. Just like skin in other parts of the body, the vulva can sometimes become irritated. Many women experience discomfort in the region of the vulva. These symptoms may be mild, but can sometimes be severe. The following questions will ask you about your vulvar skin symptoms during the past week.

During the past week, have you been bothered by:

1. Your vulva itching? 0 No 1 Yes
2. Your vulva burning or stinging? 0 No 1 Yes
3. Your vulva hurting? 0 No 1 Yes
4. Your vulva being irritated? 0 No 1 Yes
5. Your vulva being dry? 0 No 1 Yes
6. Discharge from your vulva or vagina? 0 No 1 Yes
7. Odor from your vulva or vagina? 0 No 1 Yes
8. Worry about your vulvar symptoms?
(for example, that it will spread, get worse, scar, etc.) 0 No 1 Yes
9. The appearance of your vulva? 0 No 1 Yes
10. Frustration about your vulvar symptoms? 0 No 1 Yes
11. Embarrassment about your vulvar symptoms? 0 No 1 Yes
12. The effects of your vulvar symptoms on your interactions with others? 0 No 1 Yes
13. The effects of your vulvar symptoms on your desire to be with people? 0 No 1 Yes
14. Your vulvar symptoms making it hard to show affection? 0 No 1 Yes
15. The effects of your vulvar symptoms on your daily activities? 0 No 1 Yes
16. Your vulvar symptoms affecting your desire to be intimate? 0 No 1
Yes
17. Are you currently sexually active with a partner?
 No Thank you. You are done with this questionnaire.
 Yes Please proceed with the next 4 questions
18. The effects of your vulvar symptoms on your sexual relationships? 0 No 1 Yes
19. Your vulvar symptoms causing pain during sexual activity? 0 No 1 Yes
20. Your vulvar symptoms causing dryness during sexual activity? 0 No 1 Yes

21. Your vulvar symptoms causing bleeding during sexual activity?

No Yes